

Developing International Posture Through Intensive IELTS Preparation in EFL Settings

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Abstract: *The relationship between intensive IELTS preparation and International Posture (IP) among Japanese university students is reported in this study. IP, defined as learners' openness to and willingness to engage with the international community, is a recognized factor influencing motivation and global readiness. Thirty-three students who participated in three-day IELTS workshops were compared with peers in Medical English (N = 29) and Cross-Cultural Communication (N = 16) classes using a 28-item IP questionnaire. Results showed that the IELTS group reported significantly higher IP scores than the other two groups, with no difference observed between Medical English and Cross-Cultural Communication participants. A small number of repeat IELTS participants also demonstrated significant gains, suggesting that IP is malleable and responsive to targeted instruction. These findings highlight the potential of short, exam-focused interventions to foster IP. Integrating IELTS-style speaking tasks and global issue discussions into regular classes may therefore promote both test readiness and intercultural engagement.*

Keywords: International Posture; IELTS preparation; language motivation; intercultural communication, exam-focused instruction, intercultural pedagogy

Introduction

Proficiency in English, as assessed through standardized tests such as the Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL) or International English Language Testing System (IELTS), is frequently a prerequisite for students seeking to participate in international exchange programmes. At the university where this study was conducted, medical and education students intending to study

at partner institutions in the United Kingdom and New Zealand, respectively, must take the IELTS Academic test, with programme-specific requirements ranging from 5.5 to 7.5 for overall and individual band scores. Many Japanese students, however, find the speaking component particularly challenging (IELTS.org, n.d.), due to limited practice opportunities and exposure to diverse accents, especially non-North American ones. Furthermore, students often lack a clear understanding of their strengths and weaknesses as assessed by the exam framework.

To support these students, we developed a three-day intensive IELTS preparation course that includes simulated interviews with native English speakers from a range of backgrounds. This approach helps learners identify speaking strengths and areas for improvement, while familiarizing them with different speaking styles.

Within this context, the concept of IP is defined as an individual's general interest in and willingness to engage with the international community (Yashima, 2009), is particularly relevant. IP has been identified as a key motivational factor among students considering study abroad, with higher IP associated with increased motivation to develop English skills for engagement with a diverse global community (e.g., Botes et al., 2020). Although this study focuses on Japanese university students, the findings have broader implications for EFL contexts worldwide, where learners often face high-stakes language assessments alongside limited opportunities for authentic intercultural engagement. Understanding how intensive test preparation intersects with the development of IP may be beneficial for teaching practices in similar educational environments globally.

Development of the IP Construct

A central construct in applied linguistics, IP reflects a learner's openness to engage with the international community. The construct was first operationalised through The International Posture (IP) Scale developed by Yashima (2002), which has since served as the foundation for subsequent adaptations and refinements. It has been theoretically expanded to include the following sub-components (Yashima, 2009):

- *Interest in international affairs*: Reflecting curiosity about global events, issues, and trends.
- *Willingness to interact with intercultural partners*: Representing readiness to communicate with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.
- *Intercultural communication attitudes*: Encompassing levels of comfort or anxiety when interacting across cultures.
- *World citizenship*: Denoting a sense of belonging to a global community.

Across national and educational contexts, including Japan, Korea, China, and beyond, higher IP has consistently been linked with greater motivation to learn English, willingness to communicate in English, and confidence in intercultural interactions (Aliakbari et al., 2016; Botes et al., 2020; Jiang, 2013; Kim & Kim, 2016; Nishida, 2013; Pastena & Trenchs-Parera, 2024; Willey & Suzuki, 2023; Yashima et al., 2004). While these findings highlight the benefits of IP for broader intercultural engagement, research has primarily focused on general classroom settings. Evidence suggests that classroom activities discussing global issues can foster IP (Willey & Suzuki, 2023), yet the role of intensive, exam-focused instruction, such as IELTS preparation, remains underexplored.

Previous research on IP is difficult to compare directly due to inconsistencies in how it is measured. While some researchers have adopted partial item sets from the 2009 IP scale (e.g., Kong et

al., 2018), others have relied on earlier versions (e.g., Elwood & Monoi, 2015). Even among studies using the full 2009 scale, concerns have been raised about the clarity and specificity of certain items (Mystkowska-Wiertelak & Pietrzykowska, 2011).

Two aspects of this body of research are particularly relevant to the present study: the relationship between IP and motivational patterns among Japanese learners and the idea that IP is a flexible concept that can be developed through teaching methods. Previous research has emphasised that IP can be cultivated in educational settings. For example, Willey and Suzuki (2023) claim that classroom activities involving discussions about global issues can encourage a more internationally-minded approach. The malleability of IP is of particular interest when considering how different instructional contexts, such as intensive IELTS courses, may influence learners' IP. Our research addresses this by examining the relationship between exam preparation and intercultural development in EFL contexts, specifically within short-term, intensive IELTS workshops. The insights gained from this study may inform teaching practices both in Japan and internationally.

Background

Since 2023, our institution has implemented intensive three-day IELTS preparation courses during inter-semester breaks (spring and summer 2023–2024). The IELTS is not formally included in the regular curriculum; although students take the Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC) in their first year, this test does not meet study-abroad programme requirements. As a result, students must prepare for the IELTS independently or with support from individual teachers. While these teachers are highly motivated and employ strategies to help students overcome challenges, a factor shown to sustain learner motivation (Papi & Abdollahzadeh, 2012), this approach is ultimately unsustainable and places an excessive burden on staff. The intensive courses were therefore developed to provide a structured, small-group environment (typically 10–12 students; Table 1) that allows concentrated, individualized learning. The principal objective is to assist students with limited prior preparation by familiarizing them with IELTS test formats and helping them ascertain their proficiency levels, particularly in speaking and writing.

To achieve these aims, the intensive courses make use of simulated interviews led by native-speaking (EFL) instructors, both affiliated with and external to the university. This approach provides a realistic simulation of the test environment and ensures personalized feedback. All students completed the IP questionnaire, administered in Japanese, prior to the start of the course (Appendix).

Table 1. *Participants in IELTS courses (2023–2024)*

	Medical students	Other (law, education, agriculture)	Total/ course
Course 1 (summer 2023)	7	3	10
Course 2 (spring 2024)	7	5	12
Course 3 (summer 2024)	6	5	11
Combined Total			33

Approximately 60% of attendees were first- to fourth-year medical students. This group is most likely to require IELTS certification to participate in university-sponsored UK exchange programmes.

Twenty percent of students came from the Faculty of Education, another faculty that requires students to take IELTS to participate in a faculty-supported exchange programme with New Zealand. To improve engagement, students were divided into small groups of three to four and followed a rotating schedule. Each student participated in five sessions daily, three of which focused on simulated interviews.

Student feedback was very positive. Many remarked that the intensive format helped them concentrate on key areas for improvement, while the opportunity to interact with EFL teachers from outside the university was regarded as particularly beneficial. This positive reception is consistent with the profile of learners who typically attend such workshops: students who are already motivated to engage internationally and who value authentic opportunities for communication. Consequently, we anticipated that students enrolled in these courses would demonstrate a higher IP than those participating in more conventional English classes.

Initial findings support this expectation; most students in the intensive IELTS courses had a high level of IP (mean 4.70; Table 2). This is not unexpected given the position of the IELTS exam in Japan's education system. Unlike the TOEIC, which is commonly used in Japanese university programmes and recognized for local academic and job opportunities, awareness of the IELTS among the broader student population remains comparatively limited (Baughn, 2021). Consequently, it is plausible that students possessing a pre-existing higher IP are more likely to know about the IELTS and its acceptance in countries such as the United Kingdom and New Zealand. Furthermore, the IELTS exam, particularly its in-person speaking section, is often perceived as more thorough and challenging than the TOEIC, attracting students seeking a more authentic assessment of their English skills. As one participant mentioned, "I wanted to challenge myself and learn my English speaking and writing level in an exam. Then, I can use my IELTS score to study abroad in the UK." This motivation for authentic assessment aligns with students' broader goal of preparing for study-abroad opportunities and may help explain the high levels of IP observed among workshop attendees.

Although the IELTS is less familiar to many Japanese students, its practical value in Japan is significant. While a high TOEIC score may suffice for many domestic academic and employment purposes, advanced graduate programs increasingly require TOEFL or IELTS scores. Consequently, students aiming to study or work overseas are likely drawn to the IELTS, and those voluntarily participating in intensive IELTS preparation workshops may already possess a higher level of IP even prior to the start of the courses, as initial findings appear to indicate.

Developing strong IP helps students overcome insular tendencies, often described as *uchimuki* [inward-facing] behaviour, which can limit their willingness to engage internationally (Burgess, 2015). However, fostering IP is challenging in rural or less internationalized universities, where students have limited exposure to foreign cultures and individuals. In such environments, promoting IP can encourage students to actively seek international experiences through study abroad programs, online exchanges, or more interaction with the local foreign community both in their neighborhoods and on campus.

In a more globalized world, many students who aim for jobs in multinational companies or roles that require working internationally recognize the importance of English and intercultural communication skills. As one participant explained, "I joined this course because I can't go on an exchange programme because of high cost, but I want to work for an international company after I graduate. This is my dream. My ambition." Programmes such as these, which provide opportunities

to interact with local foreign residents, may offer students a taste of going abroad, while simultaneously building their confidence in English speaking and motivating them to continue their language education. Given these considerations, two key issues concerning IP are particularly relevant to this study: the complex link between IP and motivation in learners and the crucial concept of IP's malleability or its potential for development (Botes et al., 2020).

As Willey and Suzuki (2023) suggest, well- and intentionally- designed classroom practices, especially those that provide ample opportunities for students to share their thoughts on international topics, may significantly contribute to fostering this international mindset. This cultivation of IP, in turn, is expected to support learners in achieving their larger communication goals and improve their overall motivation for language learning and intercultural engagement.

Methodology

To compare the relationship between IP, participation in intensive IELTS courses, and students enrolled in regular university classes, students were asked to complete the 28-item IP Scale in Japanese (Appendix) prior to attending the workshops (N = 33). The same questionnaire was also administered to students enrolled in two regular university classes: Medical English 1 (for 3rd-year medical students, N = 29) and Cross-Cultural Communication (for 2nd- 4th-year education faculty students, N = 16). These two comparison groups were selected because many of the participants in the IELTS workshops were drawn from these faculties. Since the questionnaire was administered to students enrolled in three different IELTS workshops, we were also able to analyse the IP of students who repeated the course.

Following data collection, responses were entered into Excel, with reverse-coded items adjusted prior to analysis, then imported into JASP (an open-source statistical analysis program). The data were first examined using descriptive statistics, including measures of central tendency (mean, median, mode) and measures of dispersion (standard deviation, variance, range, and interquartile range). To determine whether the data met the assumptions required for inferential testing, tests of normality (Shapiro-Wilk Test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) and homogeneity of variances (Levene's Test) were conducted.

Subsequently, inferential statistical analyses were carried out. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the IP levels among the three groups, followed by post-hoc tests to identify any statistically significant differences between specific groups.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics: Distribution and Central Tendency

Descriptive statistics were calculated for the IELTS, Medical English, and Cross-cultural Communication (X-culture) groups to examine the distribution and central tendencies of IP scores (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for each group

Measure	IELTS Group	Medical English Group	X-culture Group*
Mean	4.70	4.22	4.18
Standard Deviation (SD)	0.56	0.40	0.37
Variance	0.3179	0.1617	0.1379
Range	1.71 (3.57–5.28)	1.57 (3.25–4.60)	1.46 (3.28–4.75)
Interquartile Range (IQR)	0.75	0.50	0.54

A preliminary observation of these means suggests that the IELTS group exhibits a notably higher average (mean = 4.70) compared to both the Medical English (mean = 4.22) and X-culture groups (mean = 4.18). The Medical English and X-culture groups, conversely, show very similar mean scores, with only a marginal difference between them. The IELTS group also demonstrated the largest standard deviation, variance, and range, suggesting a wider dispersion of scores among its students compared to the other groups. This wider spread likely reflects the diverse motivations of IELTS participants: some were probably highly internationally minded, while others may have enrolled more pragmatically to meet university requirements for study abroad programmes, or just a desire to improve their productive English skills. The greater variability within the IELTS group, therefore, signals that exam-focused workshops can attract a broad spectrum of learners, and perhaps may include those with only emerging or developing interest in international affairs.

Assumptions for Inferential Testing

Prior to running inferential statistics, assumption tests were performed. Shapiro–Wilk tests confirmed normality across groups, and Levene’s Test indicated homogeneity of variances (Table 3). These results justified the use of a one-way ANOVA for group comparison.

Table 3. Assumption tests summary

Test	Medical English			Interpretation
	IELTS Group	Group	X Culture Group	
Shapiro-Wilk (p)	0.2066	0.0734	0.1034	Normality assumed
K-S (p)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	Non-normal (less reliable due to small n)
Levene’s Test (p)	–	–	–	0.3678 → Equal variances

Inferential Statistics: ANOVA and Post-Hoc Analysis

Having established that the assumptions for ANOVA were met, inferential statistical tests were performed to determine if the observed differences in mean scores among the IELTS, Medical English, and Cross-cultural communication groups were statistically significant. The results are summarised as follows:

Table 4. ANOVA and Post-Hoc test results

Comparison	Mean Difference	Adjusted p-value	Significant (p < 0.05)	Interpretation
ANOVA	–	0.0062	Yes	Significant difference among groups
IELTS vs Xculture	+0.52	0.0103	Yes	IELTS higher than XCulture
IELTS vs Medical English	+0.48	0.0085	Yes	IELTS higher than Medical English
Xculture vs Medical English	+0.04	0.9492	No	No significant difference

A one-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference in mean IP scores among the three groups ($p = .0062$). In this study, the decision criterion for rejecting the null hypothesis was set at $p < .05$ (95% confidence level) or $p < .01$ (99% confidence level). Post-hoc comparisons using Tukey's HSD indicated that the IELTS group scored significantly higher than both the Cross-Cultural Communication group ($p = .0103$) and the Medical English group ($p = .0085$), while no significant difference was found between the Cross-Cultural and Medical English groups ($p = .9492$). These findings suggest that students enrolled in the IELTS preparation workshops demonstrated a stronger international orientation than their peers in regular classes. This pattern may reflect self-selection of students with higher pre-existing IP, although the cross-sectional design limits any claims about causal effects of the programme. Nonetheless, the findings are consistent with the possibility that participation in an intensive, internationally oriented course may reinforce existing interest in global engagement. The workshops were promoted with an emphasis on interaction with diverse foreign residents, which may have influenced students' motivation and expectations. As one participant described, "I was excited when I learned about this intensive course. Because when I become a doctor, I may have foreign patients. I want to speak with more foreign people and learn their thoughts and experiences." This account illustrates how structured exposure to intercultural interaction can reinforce students' interest in global engagement.

The largest difference was observed between the IELTS and Cross-Cultural communication groups, which is noteworthy given that students in a Cross-Cultural communication class might be expected to exhibit higher IP. However, again, this pattern must be interpreted with caution, as students voluntarily enrolling in intensive IELTS workshops may already possess higher IP. Such self-selection complicates the interpretation of causal effects, since the observed differences could partly reflect pre-existing motivation rather than the direct impact of instruction. Even so, the results are consistent with the possibility that intensive, goal-oriented learning environments can stimulate or reinforce students' global outlook, particularly as the small number of repeat participants showed a further increase in their IP averages (Table 5). From a pedagogical perspective, the findings suggest that exam-focused courses can contribute to developing mindsets extending beyond language proficiency when they emphasize authentic speaking practice, critical writing, and engagement with global themes. Brief but carefully structured interventions, whether delivered as workshops, intensive modules, or embedded units within a semester, may foster a *glocally* engaged mindset (Robertson, 1995), helping students connect global perspectives with local contexts. Such approaches are particularly valuable in settings where opportunities for study abroad are limited.

For classroom teachers, integrating IELTS-style tasks such as mock speaking interviews, structured peer feedback, and discussions of international issues into regular instruction may further cultivate students' global orientation. Inviting local foreign community members to participate in

these activities can enhance authenticity and motivation, allowing students to engage with real-world communication while developing confidence in intercultural interactions.

Changes in IP Among Repeat Participants

To explore the malleability of IP, a subset of five students who attended the IELTS workshop multiple times was analysed (Tables 5 and 6).

Table 5. *Changes in IP means of repeat workshop participants*

Student	1st Course	2nd Course	3rd Course
Student 1	4.29	4.75	4.93
Student 2	3.57	4.11	4.32
Student 3	5.20	5.32	–
Student 4	4.64	5.14	–
Student 5	4.93	5.14	–
Mean	4.53	4.89	4.63

A paired-sample t-test comparing their IP averages before the first and second courses showed a statistically significant increase ($t(4) = -4.40, p = .012$), suggesting that students' IP improved after one cycle of intensive instruction. Although a non-parametric Wilcoxon test did not reach significance ($p = .063$), the result would suggest that future studies with more statistical power would show significance. Due to limited data ($n = 2$), changes across three course cycles could not be formally tested, but the available results suggest a potentially positive impact of repeated intensive IELTS preparation on students' IP.

Table 6. *Comparison of IP scores between first and second course*

Test	Test Statistic	p-value	Significant at $p < .05$	Interpretation
Paired t-test	$t(df) = -4.40$.012	Yes	Significant increase in IP scores from the first to the second course
Wilcoxon signed-rank test	–	.063	No	Trend toward increase; not statistically significant at .05 level

Although only two students completed a third course, both continued to show upward movement in their scores. While the sample is small, the consistency of these improvements suggests that IP is not fixed but potentially malleable, even over the course of brief interventions.

For educators and programme administrators, the results demonstrate that even short, intensive exam-focused workshops can support broader educational outcomes beyond language proficiency. The IELTS courses, emphasizing authentic speaking practice, critical writing, and engagement with global issues, appear to promote communicative openness and intercultural confidence. For Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) practitioners, several strategies emerge:

- **Authenticity:** Replicating high-stakes communication conditions (e.g., mock interviews, oral exams) can motivate students to engage more fully. Using locally based foreign instructors may further enhance this experience for participants.

- *Intensity*: Delivering instruction in focused bursts, through workshops or special class units, may amplify both skill development and international orientation.
- *Global Themes*: Designing tasks around international issues, as seen in IELTS Part 3 discussions, may encourage students to articulate opinions and perspectives that extend beyond local concerns.

By adopting these practices, teachers can use exam preparation not only to build language proficiency but also to nurture internationally engaged dispositions. The dual role of IELTS-style activities, as both exam training and intercultural preparation, demonstrates that exam-focused instruction can serve as a practical pathway to fostering a mindset that integrates local distinctiveness with global interconnectedness and global readiness in students. Future research could explore whether semester-long exposure or short intensive courses produce equivalent, greater, or different effects on IP.

Limitations

While the statistical analysis revealed significant differences in IP across groups, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the sample sizes, particularly for the cross-cultural communication group ($n = 16$) and the subgroup of students who took the IELTS course more than once ($n = 5$), were relatively small, limiting the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. Second, the analysis relied on average scores derived from the 28-item IP Scale questionnaire, which, while useful for group-level comparison, may obscure variation within specific dimensions of IP (e.g., vocational interest vs. intercultural willingness). Future research will explore these subdimensions individually to determine whether particular aspects of IP differ significantly between groups, and whether repeated participation in the IELTS course is associated with growth in certain dimensions over time.

A further limitation is self-selection. Students voluntarily enrolling in intensive IELTS workshops may already possess higher IP, complicating the interpretation of causal effects. Although repeat-participant data suggest that IP can develop through targeted instruction, it remains possible that pre-existing international orientation influenced initial enrolment. Longitudinal or randomized designs would strengthen future studies, providing more rigorous evidence of the impact of IELTS preparation on IP development.

Conclusions

This study explored whether short-term, intensive IELTS preparation workshops are associated with a higher level of IP among Japanese university students. By comparing the IP scores of students across three course types, IELTS preparation, Medical English, and Cross-Cultural Communication, we aimed to investigate both the relationship between course type and IP, and the potential for IP development through repeated participation in IELTS-focused instruction.

The findings reveal a clear and statistically significant difference in IP scores among the three groups, with the IELTS cohort demonstrating notably higher average scores than the other two. While the Medical English and cross-cultural communication groups did not differ significantly from each other, the IELTS group consistently outperformed both, suggesting a stronger

international orientation among those who voluntarily enrolled in exam-focused workshops. This may be explained in part by self-selection: students already interested in studying or working abroad are more likely to pursue IELTS preparation. However, this explanation alone does not account for the statistically significant increase (confirmed using a repeated-measures statistical test) in IP observed among repeat participants.

The analysis of a small subset of students who took the course more than once offers important insight into the malleability of IP. Even after a single cycle of instruction, participants' IP scores increased significantly. For those who returned a third time, this upward trend continued. While the sample size was limited, the consistency and direction of these changes suggest that IP is not a static trait, but a mindset that can be cultivated, particularly through meaningful, goal-oriented language education.

These findings have broader implications for internationalization strategies in higher education both in Japan and in the context of a wider global EFL setting. While much attention is often given to long-term study abroad or degree programs, this study demonstrates that even short, repeatable, and skills-focused courses, such as IELTS preparation, can contribute to fostering globally engaged attitudes. From an institutional perspective, this presents an accessible and scalable way to support students' international development, particularly in contexts where time, funding, or other constraints limit opportunities for overseas study. Overall, these findings indicate that short, targeted interventions and thoughtfully integrated classroom activities can promote a more international mindset in students, enabling them to engage meaningfully with global issues while remaining in their local environment.

At the same time, the study highlights the need for further research into the mechanisms behind IP development. Is it the intensity of the instruction, the focus on a concrete goal (such as test performance), or the students' own motivations that drive growth in international outlook? Understanding these factors more deeply would allow educators to design more targeted interventions that enhance not only language skills but also students' understanding of the local distinctiveness of their own environment and recognition of its place within the larger world system.

In conclusion, the results suggest that IELTS preparation is more than a test-oriented activity. When delivered in a focused and supportive environment, it may also play a meaningful role in shaping students' international identities and aspirations, fostering the ability to navigate and contribute to both global and local contexts.

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Appendix

The 28 Item International Posture Scale (English Translation)

When making your judgment, please refer to the following scale. For each item, write '6' if you strongly agree and '1' if you strongly disagree.

6 – Strongly agree; 5 – Agree; 4 - Somewhat agree; 3 – Somewhat disagree; 2 – Rarely agree
1 – Strongly disagree

- 1) I would like to (make more) friends with foreign students and other foreigners in Japan.
- 2) If I can avoid talking with foreigners, I usually do.
- 3) If there are international students at my school in Japan, I would try to talk to them casually.
- 4) I would not mind sharing a room in a dormitory or apartment with a foreign student.
- 5) I would like to participate in activities that help support foreigners in my community in Japan.
- 6) If a foreigner moved in next door to me in Japan, I would feel troubled.
- 7) If I saw a foreigner having trouble in a restaurant or station in Japan, I would willingly help.
- 8) I do not want to leave my hometown very much.
- 9) I would like to work in a foreign country.
- 10) I would like to work in an international organization such as the United Nations.
- 11) I am interested in doing international work.
- 12) I think events outside Japan have little to do with our daily lives.
- 13) I want to avoid jobs that involve frequent overseas business trips.
- 14) Sometimes I feel uncomfortable with the behaviour of foreigners.
- 15) I prefer to associate with people whose customs and values are similar to mine.
- 16) I enjoy cooperating with people whose customs and values differ from mine.
- 17) I would like to work with people who share similar ideas and values to mine.
- 18) I am not good at dealing with people whose customs and values differ from mine.
- 19) I often watch or read news about foreign countries.
- 20) I often discuss international affairs and events with family or friends.
- 21) I am strongly interested in international issues.
- 22) I am not very interested in overseas news.
- 23) I have many things I want to talk about with people from around the world.

- 24) There are things I would like to appeal to the world about.
- 25) I have opinions on issues such as environmental problems and the North-South problem.
- 26) When it comes to talking with people from around the world, I do not know what to say.
- 27) I do not have any particular opinions on international issues.
- 28) I have many things I want to talk about with my foreign friends.